

ANALYSIS OF THE ELEMENTS OF THE WORKING CHAMBER OF THE LINTER UNIT

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Annotation: The article provides a theoretical analysis of the design of the working chamber of the linter, graphically depicts the general design of the linter and its working chamber in the context, indicates all the elements of the chamber and their features.

Key words: Raw cotton fibers, ginning, linting, linter unit, working chamber, agitator, seed comb, saw cylinder, grate, agitator improvement

At ginneries in ginneries, raw cotton goes through several stages of separating the seeds from the pulp.

At the initial stage, the main part of the cotton fiber is separated from the seeds, this process is called ginning and is carried out by ginning machines. These machines separate up to 88-90% of the fiber.

After separation of the fiber from raw cotton, up to 10-12% of the short fiber remains in the seeds. A linter machine is used to remove it. Thus, the process of removing lint from seeds is called linting, and the machines with which this process is carried out are called linters.

Linter units have several models, but 5LP linter units are considered the most common. This model is taken as the basis of the study, both its theoretical features and its practical application, as well as the existing shortcomings, are investigated.

The working chamber is a space bounded by the front and rear apron, seed comb, grate, front bar, density valve and chamber sides. There is a stirrer inside the chamber. Through the upper part of the chamber into it from the feeder along the tray, the seeds in a uniform flow enter the working chamber along its entire width. Through the gaps between the grates, the saw blades of the rotating saw cylinder protrude into the working chamber. The saw teeth, penetrating into the mass of the seed roller, scrape off the lint from the surface of the seeds and take it out of the grate. The lint is removed from the saw teeth by an air stream injected through the nozzle of the air chamber, and carried away to the discharge part of the air chamber, and then transported through the pneumatic pipeline to the battery condenser.

Let's take a closer look at the working chamber of the linter:

Fig.2 Scheme of the working chamber of the linter

1-working chamber; 2-rotator; 3-seed comb; 4-saw cylinder; 5 grate; 6-layer seeds.

The tedder plays a huge role in the process of linting cotton, which is why the tedder is widely studied by scientists, since the improvement of its design can increase the productivity of the entire unit. To date, our scientists have carried out many studies of the linter working

chamber agitator , but the question of the perfection of this element remains open so far, because the improvements made have positive aspects, leading to an increase in the unit's performance, but at the same time have negative consequences due to which do not allow to achieve high performance in their application.

Conclusion:

When studying the operation of the unit at cotton ginning enterprises, it was revealed that it was necessary to find a practical solution to this problem, which would allow using the created design and obtaining good results, because at the moment the previously created designs were not used for a long time, after identifying the side effects of the introduced changes in the design of the turner , these models have been retired.

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